

Effect of Problem-Solving Skill Training Therapy on Aggressive Behaviours of Secondary School Students in Calabar Nigeria

M. O. Ajah¹, M. O. Okon², C. B. Ekarika², E. J. Udosen³

¹Institute of Education, University of Calabar, Nigeria

²Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, Nigeria

³Ministry of Education Akwa Ibom State Nigeria

Abstract

Frequent display of aggressive behaviours among students in schools, amid security challenges, strikes and effects of Covid-19 pandemic has and is still threatening the overall wellbeing and safety of the school environment, larger society, and the attainment of our national educational goals. The need to curb aggression particularly among secondary school adolescents/youths is the main concern of this study. The study therefore was designed to investigate the effect of Problem-Solving Skill Training Therapy (PSST) in reducing different forms of students' aggression in Calabar Nigeria. The interaction effect of gender and treatment was also investigated. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted. Simple random sampling technique was used to select two intact classes with a sample of 94 subjects from two sampled schools. Simple random sampling technique was also used to assign the intact classes to the experimental and control groups involved in the study. A questionnaire tagged Behaviour Assessment Questionnaire for Secondary School Students (BAQSSS) with a reliability coefficient of 0.952 was used for data collection. Descriptive statistics and Multivariate Analysis of Covariance were used for data analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that problem solving skill training therapy (PSST) reduced only physical and verbal aggressions of students but did not significantly reduce their social and overall aggression. The result also showed that the interaction effect of treatment and gender was not significant. It was recommended that behavioural therapies such as PSST should replace punishment in handling students who manifest those forms of aggressive behaviours it can control.

Keywords: Problem Solving Skill, Aggressive behaviours, Students, Behavioural therapy.

Introduction

A highly disturbing trend has been observed whereby in their interaction with others, students often manifested a high degree of aggression, which calls for urgent intervention by all stakeholders. Aggression is a universal, social, and complex behaviour that expresses negative emotions that tend to hurt someone physically or psychologically (Shireem & Sufiana, 2015). The prevalence of aggressive behaviours among students in most schools globally has been established in literature (Ajah, 2019; Okeke & Obi, 2015; Ikwuba 2011). De Frutos (2013) noted its effects on approximately 10% of students from twelve to eighteen years of age.

worldwide. It manifests in the form of extortion, physical violation, nasty rumors, exclusion from group, damage of property, threats and so on. It is most usually linked with conduct disorder that could upset people, disrupt basic social norms, and cause breakdown of relationships. It can manifest as verbal abuse, physical attack, or social exclusion. Different types of aggressive behaviours are common among the students in most of the schools in the city. Based on the survey that was carried out by the researchers, it was discovered that, all the gates of the schools visited were manned by members of Nigerian Peace Corps whose presence in the schools was evidence that teachers alone can no longer control the students. Some students gang up to beat up their teachers for disciplining them. Some come to school with daggers to fight among rival groups while some are into cultism and substance abuses. Others disrupt lessons, insult teachers, hurt, intimidate, and frighten other students. In Calabar Nigeria, evidence of school dropouts in alliance with students currently in school constituting themselves into nuisance groups such as the "Bedside Boys", "Scolombo boys", Ekpat and other cult groups using aggression to terrorize and create insecurity in the area abound, (Ajah, 2019; Okon, 2013).

Frequent display of aggressive behaviours among students in secondary schools is a serious social problem which threatens their overall wellbeing and the safety of the school environment (Spiegler & Guevremont, 2003). The aggressive behaviours of youths in secondary schools are inimical to development and it disrupts the harmonious balance of the normally positive school environment, thereby hampering learning process and limits the learning potentials of willing students (Denga & Denga in Okon 2010). Hughes and Carell in Gallagher (2009) noted that childhood aggression in school is highly prognostic of maladaptive consequences such as delinquencies, substance abuse, under-achievement, school dropout and criminal activities which might be perpetuated in the larger society by the victims or perpetrators of the problem behaviour. The atmosphere of insecurity might lead to ineffective learning. The perpetrators themselves if not stopped, might develop a carryover syndrome. Families also suffer the consequences of aggression; parents no longer have confidence in most schools for the security of their children, resulting in mass shopping for schools and exodus of students from one school to another each new academic year. This attempt by parents in seeking schools that offer favourable growth and development environments for their children has led to some children attending more than three schools by the end of their secondary school programme.

Several efforts made by major stakeholders such as parents, school management, and teachers towards addressing the problem have not yielded the desired results probably because the aversive measures such as physical punishments which are being used most often, have short term positive impact. (The American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry, 2022) Moreover, most of the studies carried out around aggression attempted to investigate the causes of the behaviour instead of the solution (Okon, 2010; Ikwuba, 2011; Shireem & Sufiana 2015). According to behavioural theorists like Bandura, aggression is learned. (Tutor2u, 2021) and any learned behaviour can be well be explained by...

Currently, psychologists have advocated the importance of direct interventions involving the use of psychotherapies which are preferred as opposed to physical punishment. It was on this premise that the present researchers were urged to explore the possibility of using psychotherapy intervention strategy. In this research, the psychotherapy isolated for study and intervention which is also the main independent variable, is Problem- Solving Skills Training Therapy (PSST).

Problem- Solving Skills Training Therapy (PSST) is a type of cognitive behavioural coping skills therapy under cognitive behavioural therapy that deals with cognitive processes such as faulty perceptions and decision making during social interaction that leads to hostile attribution bias and inability to generate alternative solutions to problems that may contribute to aggressive behaviours. Problem-solving skills training according to Spiegler and Guevremout (2003), refers to a systematic process by which a person generates a variety of potentially effective solutions to a problem; judiciously chooses the best of these solutions; implements and evaluates the chosen solution. Problem- solving training teaches problem- solving skills as a general coping strategy for dealing with problems that may arise during daily life. Here, clients are taught to analyse interpersonal conflicts, to develop non- aggressive solutions and think about the consequences of their actions in problematic situations. It is a therapy designed for populations which are at risk of developing psychological disorders, for example, adolescents who have difficulty controlling anger (Tarrier, Kinney, McCarthy, Humphreys, Wittrowski, & Shi, 2000), because harmful aggression involves a great deal of anger. Specifically, this behaviour therapy is beneficial to individuals with behaviour problems that involve conflict, of which aggression is one of them. It prepares clients to deal with future problems on their own, which may help prevent psychological disorders from developing. Moreover, its efficacy has been demonstrated in previous studies such as Guevremont and Foster in Spiegler and Guevremont, (2003); Ang, (2010); Anliak and Sahium (2010); Peacock (2010); Abdulmalik, Ani, Ajuwom and Omigbodun, (2016).

Vaughn and Bullock in Ajah, (2019) also evaluated the efficacy of an interpersonal problem- solving training programme with aggressive young children. The result of the analysis reflected the efficacy of the training procedure and the nature of the change in interpersonal problem-solving behaviour in aggressive young children that received the training. Many previous studies such as Landenberger and Lipsey 2005, Swokwule in Ojewola 2014; Smeet, Leeijen, Vandermolen, Scheeper, Buitelaar, & Pammelise, 2014; Smeet 2017), provided strong indications of the effectiveness of psychological interventions in the treatment of psychological problems. At the same time, there are also several proofs of variations in treatment effect and effect size (Landenberger & Lipsey 2005). The variations in treatment effect have been attributed to moderator or mediator variables. (Kechey, Storch, Menlo and Geffken in Knopp and Lopez 2013). A moderator variable is a third variable that can affect direction and/or the strength of the relationship between a dependent and independent variable in a study. In line with the above assertion, it was considered necessary to introduce a moderator variable to determine its influence on the outcome of the treatment. The moderator variable considered in this study is gender, which is marked as male or female.

In their study, Lauderberger et al, (2005) identified gender as among the characteristics of the participant that may influence the outcome of CBT. Weisz et al (1995) revealed that adolescent girls showed better treatment outcomes than other ages and gender group. However, in his study Ojewola (2014) no significant difference between male and female subjects in both the experimental and control groups was shown. Related studies such as Cuijpers, *et al.* (2014), Landenberger and Lipsey (2005), Daryoush, D'Souza, and Ebrahim, (2012) etc showed no gender effect on treatment outcome. In support of the above findings, Eifediyi, (2015), Brown, Fite and Poquiz (2016) revealed no gender difference in the associations with treatment. Furthermore, Smeet, (2017) posited that gender and onset of problems (before the age 10 or later) could also have influence on the degree to which aggressive symptoms are expressed by the children. This can also probably affect response to treatment. In the study of Smeet, Leeijen, Vandermolen, Scheeper, Buitelaar, and Rommelise (2015) gender and age did not moderate treatment effect in the meta-analysis study.

The dependent variable of the study is students' aggressive behaviours, and this is operationally defined in terms of physical, verbal, and social aggression. Physical aggression is behaviour that causes or threatens physical harms towards others. Verbal aggression is the use of words to cause assault on another person's self-concept in order to deliver psychological pain while social aggression is a non-physical form of aggression that is meant to inflict or threaten damage to relationships or some one's social reputation.

In addition to ascertaining the effectiveness of PSST in reducing the aggressive behaviours of students in the study area, the present study went further to determine the extent it reduced different dimensions of aggression. Researches on interaction effect of moderator variable such as gender, on the CBT treatment outcomes on aggressive behaviours showed mix reports. Many of the studies reviewed supported no interaction effect of gender and treatment, while few related studies found significant interaction effect. Even at that, none of the studies from the two different groups above attempted the interaction effect of PSST and gender on the different forms of aggression. Again, there is obvious dearth of literature as it relates to interaction effect of PSST and gender on aggressive behaviours of students. Therefore, more studies are needed to be carried out on the moderators of treatment effect of PSST. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of exposure to problem solving skill training therapy (PSST) on aggressive behaviours of secondary school students in Calabar, Metropolis, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined:

- i. the main effect of exposure to problem solving skill training therapy (PSST) on students' (physical, verbal, and social) aggressive behaviours;
- ii. the interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' aggression

The following two research questions were answered in the study:

1. To what extent will exposure to problem-solving skill training therapy (PSST) affect student's aggressive behaviours?
2. What is the interaction effect of problem-solving skill training therapy (treatment) and gender on students' aggressive behaviours?

In their study, Lauderberger et al, (2005) identified gender as among the characteristics of the participant that may influence the outcome of CBT. Weisz et al (1995) revealed that adolescent girls showed better treatment outcomes than other ages and gender group. However, in his study Ojewola (2014) no significant difference was shown between male and female subjects in both the experimental and control groups was shown. Related studies such as Cuijpers, *et al.* (2014), Landenberger and Lipsey (2005), Daryoush, D'Souza, and Ebrahim, (2012) etc showed no gender effect on treatment outcome. In support of the above findings, Eifediyi, (2015), Brown, Fite and Poquiz (2016) revealed no gender difference in the associations with treatment. Furthermore, Smeet, (2017) posited that gender and onset of problems (before the age 10 or later) could also have influence on the degree to which aggressive symptoms are expressed by the children. This can also probably affect response to treatment. In the study of Smeet, Leeijen, Vandermolen, Scheeper, Buitelaar, and Rommelise (2015) gender and age did not moderate treatment effect in the meta-analysis study.

The dependent variable of the study is students' aggressive behaviours, and this is operationally defined in terms of physical, verbal, and social aggression. Physical aggression is behaviour that causes or threatens physical harms towards others. Verbal aggression is the use of words to cause assault on another person's self- concept in order to deliver psychological pain while social aggression is a non-physical form of aggression that is meant to inflict or threaten damage to relationships or some one's social reputation.

In addition to ascertaining the effectiveness of PSST in reducing the aggressive behaviours of students in the study area, the present study went further to determine the extent it reduced different dimensions of aggression. Researches on interaction effect of moderator variable such as gender, on the CBT treatment outcomes on aggressive behaviours showed mix reports. Many of the studies reviewed supported no interaction effect of gender and treatment, while few related studies found significant interaction effect. Even at that, none of the studies from the two different groups above attempted the interaction effect of PSST and gender on the different forms of aggression. Again, there is obvious dearth of literature as it relates to interaction effect of PSST and gender on aggressive behaviours of students. Therefore, more studies are needed to be carried out on the moderators of treatment effect of PSST. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of exposure to problem solving skill training therapy (PSST) on aggressive behaviours of secondary school students in Calabar, Metropolis, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined:

- i. the main effect of exposure to problem solving skill training therapy (PSST) on students' (physical, verbal, and social) aggressive behaviours;
- ii. the interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' aggression

The following two research questions were answered in the study:

1. To what extent will exposure to problem-solving skill training therapy (PSST) affect student's aggressive behaviours?
2. What is the interaction effect of problem solving skill training therapy (treatment) and gender on students' aggressive behaviours?

- 1. Determine the hypotheses were tested in the study.
- 2. Explain the significant effect of problem-solving skill training through mathematics on students' aggressive behaviour.
- 3. Discuss the significant negative effect of problem-solving skill training through mathematics on students' aggressive behaviour.

Method

A non-experimental design was used in the study. The study was carried out in a secondary school in Lagos, Nigeria. The area is characterized by high unemployment rate which often leads to student activities that affect the school. This study intended to measure the effect of problem-solving skill training through mathematics on the students' aggressive behaviour in the area. The design of the study compares the 120 students who were trained in the metacognitive problem-solving technique with a sample of 60 students from the control schools. Simple random sampling technique was also used to assign the three classes of the experimental groups involved in the study. 40 of the subjects were male while 20 were female. The 40 and 20 were respectively. The 60 subjects used in the study were divided into control group (N = 60) and experimental group (N = 60). The 40 subjects in the control group (N = 60) were male while 20 were female. Out of the 40 subjects in Experimental group, 10, 10, and 20 were respectively.

The instrument used in this collection was a questionnaire given to students in the Department of Secondary School Students (DSSS). The DSSS is a questionnaire instrument A and B. Segment A requests for demographic information such as sex, age, and school while B was designed to elicit information about aggressive behaviour. This segment has three sub-sections: B¹ of physical aggression, B² of verbal aggression and B³ of sexual aggression. Segment B was measured using 20 items on a four-point Likert scale. Physical and sexual aggressions were measured with 10, 10 and 4 items respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts in educational measurement in the department of arts and measurements in the University of Lagos. The instrument is presented in appendix 1.

The alpha stability procedure was used to measure the stability of the instrument. The overall scale had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.85. The subscales physical aggression, verbal aggression, and sexual aggression had coefficients of 0.80, 0.80 and 0.80. The stability coefficient of the overall scale was adjusted high enough to show a high reliability. The SPSS 20.0 software package was also developed to be executed. The reliability procedure of the SPSS software package was used to measure the reliability of the instrument in the two and three subscales.

Following two hypotheses were tested in the study:
 There is no significant effect of problem-solving skill training therapy on students' aggressive behaviours?
 There is no significant interaction effect of problem-solving skill training therapy (treatment) and gender on students' aggressive behaviours

Method

The non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group type of quasi experimental design with two intact classes was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Calabar metropolis, Nigeria. Calabar was the first administrative capital city of the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The area is characterized by incessant youth unrest which often leads to violent activities that affect the schools in the area. This actually informed the researcher's choice of Calabar as the area for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 3204 senior secondary school two intact classes with a sample of 94 subjects from two sampled schools. Simple random sampling technique was also used to assign the intact classes to the experimental and control groups involved in the study. 42 of the subjects were male while 52 were female i.e., 44.7% and 55.3% respectively. The 94 subjects used for this study were categorized as follows: control group (N = 47 i.e., 50%), experimental group (N = 47 i.e., 50%). Out of the 47 subjects in the Control Group 25 (53.2%) were males while 22 (46.8%) were females. Out of the 47 subjects in Experimental Group, 17(36.1%) were males while 30 (63.8%) were females.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire tagged Behaviour and Attitude Questionnaire for Secondary School Students (BAQSSS). The BAQSSS is divided into two segments: A and B. Segment 'A' requested for demographic information such as sex, age, and school while 'B' was designed to elicit information on aggressive behaviours. This segment has three sub-divisions: B1, B2 and B3 for Physical aggression, B2 for Verbal aggression and B3 for Social aggression. Segment B was measured using 30 items on a four – point Likert type scale. Physical, verbal, and social aggressions were measured with 11, 10 and 9 items respectively.

The instrument was validated by three experts: two in educational psychology and one in the department of tests and measurements in the University of Calabar. The instrument is presented in appendix 1.

The Alpha reliability procedure was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument. The overall scale had a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.901. The sub-scales: physical aggression, verbal aggression, and social aggression had reliability coefficients of 0.891, 0.896 and 0.910. The reliability coefficient for the instrument was adjudged high enough for them to be used in the study. The treatment package was also developed by the researcher. The validity procedures of the PSST treatment package was assessed by the researcher through its face and content validity.

Table 2
Extent of effect of exposure to PSST on aggression

Variable	Control group				Treatment group				$\bar{X}$ diff	$\bar{X}$ diff. b/w Contr. and exp.
	N	Pre-test	Post-test	$\bar{X}$ diff.	N	Pre-test	Post-test	$\bar{X}$ diff		
Physical Aggression	47	26.57	25.87	0.7	47	27.36	19.36	8.0	-7.3	
Verbal Aggression	47	28.55	23.74	4.81	47	29.44	21.91	7.53	-2.72	
Social aggression	47	29.00	26.97	2.03	47	29.25	21.91	7.34	-5.31	
Overall aggression	47	90.19	76.51	13.68	47	90.72	72.80	17.92	-4.24	

In responding to this question, the pre-test and post-test mean differences of the subjects were used to estimate the extent to which exposure to PSST may have exerted some effects on the subjects' level of aggression (physical, verbal, social and overall). As presented in Table 2, the mean differences between the students' pre-test and post-test scores in the various components of aggression vary between the control and the experimental groups. For the control group, the mean differences between the pre-test and post-test scores range from 0.7 in physical aggression, to 13.68 in the overall aggression. For the experimental group, the corresponding differences between the pre-test and post-test mean differences range from 7.34 in respect of social aggression to 17.9 in the overall aggression. The results in Table 2 show that the differences between the mean pre-test and post-test differences of the control and the experimental groups range from -2.72 in verbal aggression, to -7.3 in physical aggression. This, points to a noticeable difference in the manifest aggression of students after exposure to treatment using PSST; thus implying that the behavioural therapeutic intervention reduced all the dimensions of aggression considered in the study. The reduction was however not statistically significant for all the different dimensions of aggression.

In order to ascertain the extent to which exposure to PSST reduced their aggression, the subjects were categorised into three levels: Marginal, Moderate and Potential. Subjects for whom differences between pre-test and post-test manifest aggression were below the group mean difference were classified as subjects who manifested marginal reduction in aggression following treatment with PSST; those whose differences were within the group mean differences were categorised as those who manifested moderate aggression reduction following treatment; and those whose differences were above the group mean differences, were categorised as those who manifested substantial reduction in aggression after treatment. The data were further analysed by testing a hypothesis using Multivariate analysis of covariance to establish if the effect could be statistically significant.

The results of the significant main effect of problem-solving skill training/therapy (PSST) on aggression in the various behaviours (physical, verbal, social and overall aggression).

Table 3
Multivariate analysis of covariance MANCOVA of PSST on students' aggressive behaviour

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD
Physical aggression	Control group	47	25.87	5.80
	Expt group	47	19.36	3.62
	Total	94	22.61	5.82
Verbal aggression	Control group	47	23.74	5.52
	Expt group	47	21.91	3.64
	Total	94	22.82	4.74
Social aggression	Control group	47	26.97	5.61
	Expt group	47	25.02	4.49
	Total	94	26.00	5.15
Overall aggression	Control group	47	76.51	13.97
	Expt group	47	72.80	11.75
	Total	94	74.65	12.97

	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Physical aggression	1048.656 ^a	5	209.731	8.782	.000
	Verbal aggression	304.706 ^b	5	60.941	2.995	.015
	Social aggression	242.813 ^c	5	48.563	1.919	.099
	Overall aggression	849.815 ^d	5	169.963	1.010	.417
Group	Physical aggression	1009.922	1	1009.922	42.289	.000
	Verbal aggression	85.048	1	85.048	4.180	.044
	Social aggression	93.004	1	93.004	3.675	.058
	Overall aggression	336.427	1	336.427	1.999	.161
Error	Physical aggression	2101.556	88	23.881		
	Verbal aggression	1790.571	88	20.347		
	Social aggression	1227.187	88	25.309		
	Overall aggression	14813.292	88	168.333		

Physical aggression	51234.000	94
Verbal aggression	51088.000	94
Social aggression	66014.000	94
Overall aggression	539624.000	94
Physical aggression	3150.213	93
Verbal aggression	2095.277	93
Social aggression	2470.000	93
Overall aggression	15663.106	93

Corrected Total
R Squared = .333 (Adjusted R Squared = .295)

As presented in Table 3, the results of the MANCOVA analysis show that the calculated F-values for physical aggression, $F(1, 88) = 42.289, p < 0.05$ and verbal aggression, $F(1, 88) = 4.180, p < 0.05$ are each greater than the critical F-value of 3.95 at 1 and 88 degrees of freedom, at 0.05 level of significance. The calculated F-values for social aggression $F(1, 88) = 3.675, p > 0.05$ and for the overall aggression $F(1, 88) = 1.999, p > 0.05$ are each less than the critical F-value of 3.95 at 1 and 88 degrees of freedom. With these results, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of PSST on students' aggressive behaviours is rejected in respect of physical and verbal aggression and upheld in respect of social and overall aggression. The alternate hypothesis that PSST has a significant effect in reducing physical and verbal aggression in students is accepted. The capacity of PSST to reduce social and overall aggression in students is not statistically significant. One can then confidently conclude that intervention through PSST therapy can effectively reduce only physical and verbal aggression in students. It is not very effective in controlling social and overall aggression.

Research question two: What is the interaction effect of problem-solving skill training (PSST) and gender on students' aggressive behaviours?

In answering to this question, the pre-test and post-test mean differences of the aggressive behaviours were used to estimate the extent to which exposure to PSST and gender of the students have exerted some effects on their level of aggression (physical, verbal, social and overall).

Table 4
Interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggressive behaviours

Variables	Group	Gender	N	Level of aggression reduction			
				Marginally%	Moderately%	Substantial%	Total%
Physical aggression	Control	Male	25	56.0	16.0	28	100
		Female	22	59.1	9.1	31.8	100
		Total	47	57.4	12.8	29.8	100
	Expt	Male	17	29.4	11.8	58.8	100
		Female	30	50.0	3.3	46.7	100
		Total	47	42.6	6.4	51.1	100
Verbal aggression	Control	Male	25	48.0	0	52.0	100
		Female	22	63.6	9.1	27.3	100
		Total	47	55.3	9.1	40.4	100
	Expt	Male	17	52.9	5.9	41.2	100
		Female	30	33.3	16.7	50.0	100
		Total	47	40.4	12.8	46.8	100
Social aggression	Control	Male	25	44.0	8.0	48.0	100
		Female	22	40.9	18.2	40.9	100
		Total	47	42.6	12.8	44.7	100
	Expt	Male	17	52.9	23.5	23.5	100
		Female	30	50.0	23.3	26.7	100
		Total	47	51.1	23.4	25.5	100
Overall aggression	Control	Male	25	56.0	0	44.0	100
		Female	22	59.1	0	40.9	100
		Total	47	57.4	0	42.6	100
	Expt	Male	17	47.1	0	52.9	100
		Female	30	43.3	17.6	35.3	100
		Total	47	44.7	10.6	44.7	100

As presented in Table 4, there was a substantial interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggressive behaviours. For the total group, majority of the subjects (51.1%) manifested a substantially reduced physical aggression following PSST treatment. About 42.6% and 6.4% respectively manifested marginal and moderate reduction of physical aggression. On gender effect, given that 40.4% of the subjects

46.7% of the female subjects manifested substantial reduction, a marked difference exists between the proportions of male and female subjects that the therapy affected. As the figures show, the treatment with PSST had a more consequential effect on males than females in respect of physical aggression.

Again, majority of the subjects (46.8%) manifested a substantially reduced verbal aggression following the PSST treatment. About 40.4% and 12.8% respectively manifested marginal and moderate reduction of verbal aggression. On gender effect, given the fact that about 50.0% of the female subjects manifested substantially reduced verbal aggression as a result of the therapy, while 41.2% of the male subjects manifested substantial reduction, a marked difference also exists between the proportions of male and female subjects that the therapy affected. The figures show that treatment with PSST had a more consequential effect on female subjects over and above male subjects in respect of verbal aggression.

As also presented in Table 4, 25.5% of the subjects manifested a substantially reduced social aggression following the PSST treatment while about 51.1% and 23.4% respectively manifested marginal and moderate reduction of social aggression. Based on gender effect, 26.7% of the female subjects manifested substantially reduced social aggression as a result of the therapy while 23.5% of the male subjects manifested substantial reduction. The figures show a slight difference between the proportions of male and female subjects that the therapy affected. This means the treatment with PSST had most comparable effect on female and male subjects in respect of social aggression.

The results still as presented in Table 4, show that 44.7% of the subjects manifested a substantially reduced overall aggression following the PSST treatment. About 44.7% and 10.6% respectively manifested marginal and moderate reduction of overall aggression. On gender effect, 50.0% of female subjects and 35.3% of male subjects manifested substantial reduction. A marked difference exists between the proportions of female and male subjects that the therapy affected. As shown by the figures, the treatment with PSST had a more consequential effect on females than males in respect of overall aggression. Based on this result, it is concluded that, there was significant interaction effect of PSST and gender on aggressive behaviours of secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis Nigeria. The data were further analysed by testing the hypothesis using the Multivariate analysis of covariance to establish whether the null hypothesis could be statistically significant.

In the null form, the second hypothesis states thus: there is no significant interaction effect of problem-solving skill training therapy (PSST) and gender on aggression (physical, verbal, social and overall aggression). To test the hypothesis, the multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was used to analyse the data.

Table 5
Multivariate analysis of covariance of PSST and gender on students' aggression

Variable	Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD
Physical aggression	Control	Male	25	26.1200	5.06063
		Female	22	25.5909	6.65947
		Total	47	25.8723	5.80336
	Expt	Male	17	19.4118	2.80755
		Female	30	19.3333	4.06273
		Total	47	19.3617	3.62615
Verbal aggression	Control	Male	25	23.2000	5.85947
		Female	22	24.3636	5.18740
		Total	47	23.7447	5.52649
	Expt	Male	17	22.7647	4.11597
		Female	30	21.4333	3.32891
		Total	47	21.9149	3.64650
Social aggression	Control	Male	25	26.4800	5.22909
		Female	22	27.5455	6.10017
		Total	47	26.9787	5.61632
	Expt	Male	17	25.9412	3.73280
		Female	30	24.5000	4.85479
		Total	47	25.0213	4.49391
Overall aggression	Control	Male	25	76.5200	13.73293
		Female	22	76.5000	14.56594
		Total	47	76.5106	13.97338
	Expt	Male	17	74.5882	8.39687
		Female	30	71.8000	13.32201
		Total	47	72.8085	11.75777

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Physical aggression	1053.287 ^a	7	150.470	6.171	.000
	Verbal aggression	324.510 ^b	7	46.359	2.251	.038
	Social aggression	272.374 ^c	7	38.911	1.523	.170
	Overall aggression	899.801 ^d	7	128.543	.749	.631
Group* Sex	Physical aggression	3.225	1	3.225	.132	.717
	Verbal aggression	19.443	1	19.443	.944	.334
	Social aggression	28.728	1	28.728	1.124	.292
	Overall aggression					

Table 5
Multivariate analysis of covariance of PSST and gender on students' aggression

Variable	Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD
Physical aggression	Control	Male	25	26.1200	5.06063
		Female	22	25.5909	6.65947
		Total	47	25.8723	5.80336
	Expt	Male	17	19.4118	2.80755
		Female	30	19.3333	4.06273
		Total	47	19.3617	3.62615
Verbal aggression	Control	Male	25	23.2000	5.85947
		Female	22	24.3636	5.18740
		Total	47	23.7447	5.52649
	Expt	Male	17	22.7647	4.11597
		Female	30	21.4333	3.32891
		Total	47	21.9149	3.64650
Social aggression	Control	Male	25	26.4800	5.22909
		Female	22	27.5455	6.10017
		Total	47	26.9787	5.61632
	Expt	Male	17	25.9412	3.73280
		Female	30	24.5000	4.85479
		Total	47	25.0213	4.49391
Overall aggression	Control	Male	25	76.5200	13.73293
		Female	22	76.5000	14.56594
		Total	47	76.5106	13.97338
	Expt	Male	17	74.5882	8.39687
		Female	30	71.8000	13.32201
		Total	47	72.8085	11.75777

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Physical aggression	1053.287 ^a	7	150.470	6.171	.000
	Verbal aggression	324.510 ^b	7	46.359	2.251	.038
	Social aggression	272.374 ^c	7	38.911	1.523	.170
	Overall aggression	899.801 ^d	7	128.543	.749	.631
Group* Sex	Physical aggression	3.225	1	3.225	.132	.717
	Verbal aggression	19.443	1	19.443	.944	.334
	Social aggression	28.728	1	28.728	1.124	.292
	Overall aggression					

a particular therapy than to another. For instance, in Ajah 2019, the differences of aggression were reduced by rational emotive behavioural therapy. The findings of this study seem to agree with Guevremont and Foster in Guevremont, (2003) who reported that treatment of children's aggression with PSST may produce changes of limited magnitude and durability, which may be likened to the different levels of manifest aggression by the students after exposure to PSST treatment package, although they did not go into details of aggression as was done by this study. The finding of this study also corroborates those of Abdulmalik et al (2016) who reported that PSST interventions for aggressive behaviours among primary school children showed significant reduction in teachers' and students related aggressive behaviours. Again, their study dealt with primary school pupils unlike this study that is on secondary school students. Related to those of Vaughn and Bullock in Ajah, (2019), Ang (2010), Bushman and Gelles (2010), and Anliak and Sahim (2010) who reported the effectiveness of problem-solving strategies in managing some problem behaviours are consistent with the findings of the study. However, this study differs from those studies in that it found the effect of PSST on the different forms of aggressive behaviours of physical, verbal, social and overall aggressive behaviours.

The findings of this study could be attributed to the fact that PSST may be effective in handling all the different forms of aggression, as such; it may not be combined with other therapies that may be effective in handling the problem which could not handle. Again, this result could be attributed to the fact that PSST evaluates the consequences of an action before taking decision to carry on or not to carry on with the action. The consequences of physical and verbal aggression are visible and can be noticed since they involve overt actions, unlike social aggression that involves hidden actions. The mean score difference of social aggression may have exerted some effect on that of overall aggression thereby contributing to its non-significant effect.

The result of the analysis also showed that there was substantial interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggression and the interaction effect was significant in different patterns. More male subjects gained substantially in physical aggression than female subjects while in verbal, social and overall aggression, more female subjects gained substantially than males. However, when a hypothesis was tested to determine the significance of the interaction effect, using MANCOVA, the result of the analysis revealed no statistically significant interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggressive behaviour. The finding means that the therapy was not gender bias. The study revealed no statistically significant interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggressive behaviours who responded to PSST treatment therapy with lower mean scores. No direct study on the interaction effect of PSST and gender on aggressive behaviours of students was found, but just like in the case of other cognitive behavioural therapies such as Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy, the findings of this study agrees with that of some related studies such as Daryoush *et al* (2012); Ojewole (2014); Cuijper *et al* (2014); Eifediyi (2015) and, Smeet *et al* (2015), who investigated the effectiveness of CBT on problem behaviours of students and reported no interaction effect of treatment and gender on the outcomes. Contrary to the findings of the study,

a particular therapy than to another. For instance, in Ajah 2019, the different dimensions of aggression were reduced by rational emotive behavioural therapy (REBT). The findings of this study seem to agree with Guevremont and Foster in Spiegler, and Guevremont, (2003) who reported that treatment of children's aggressive behaviour with PSST may produce changes of limited magnitude and durability. Their position may be likened to the different levels of manifest aggression by the students in this study after exposure to PSST treatment package, although they did not go into different forms of aggression as was done by this study. The finding of this study also corroborates that of Abdulmalik et al (2016) who reported that PSST interventions for aggressive behaviours among primary school children showed significant reduction in both teachers' and students related aggressive behaviours. Again, their study dealt on primary school pupils unlike this study that is on secondary school students. Related studies as those of Vaughn and Bullock in Ajah, (2019), Ang (2010), Bushman and Peacock (2010), and Anliak and Sahim (2010) who reported the effectiveness of different problem-solving strategies in managing some problem behaviours are consistent with the findings of the study. However, this study differs from those studies in the sense that it found the effect of PSST on the different forms of aggressive behaviours of students: physical, verbal, social and overall aggressive behaviours.

The findings of this study could be attributed to the fact that PSST may not be effective in handling all the different forms of aggression, as such; it may need to be combined with other therapies that may be effective in handling the problem areas it could not handle. Again, this result could be attributed to the fact that PSST evaluates the consequences of an action before taking decision to carry on or not to carry on with the action. The consequences of physical and verbal aggression are visible and can easily be noticed since they involve overt actions, unlike social aggression that involves covert actions. The mean score difference of social aggression may have exerted some impact on that of overall aggression thereby contributing to its non-significant effect.

The result of the analysis also showed that there was substantial interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggression and the interaction effect took different patterns. More male subjects gained substantially in physical aggression than female subjects while in verbal, social and overall aggression, more female subjects gained substantially than males. However, when a hypothesis was tested to determine the significance of the interaction effect, using MANCOVA, the result of the analysis revealed no statistically significant interaction effect of PSST and gender on students' aggressive behaviour. The finding means that the therapy was not gender bias. The treatment focused on the problem irrespective of gender. It reduced both males and female students' aggressive behaviours who responded to PSST treatment therapy with lower mean scores. No direct study on the interaction effect of PSST and gender on aggressive behaviours of students was found, but just like in the case of other cognitive behavioural therapies such as Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy, the findings of the study agrees with that of some related studies such as Daryoush *et al* (2012); Ojewola (2014); Cuiper *et al* (2014); Lafediya (2015) and, Smeets *et al* (2015), who investigated the effectiveness of CBT on problem behaviours of students and reported no interaction effect of treatment and gender on the outcomes. Contrary to the findings of the study.

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made:

- a. Problem-solving skill training therapy can significantly reduce physical and verbal aggression but cannot reduce students' social and overall aggression. It was then concluded that PSST as a single therapy cannot be effective in reducing all the different dimensions of aggression.
- b. It was also concluded that interaction effect of treatment and gender does not significantly affect the treatment outcomes. The findings of this study have implications for both educational and national development.

Recommendations

The paper therefore recommends that:

1. Ministry of Education should organize seminars and workshops for teachers and school counselors to train them on the use of psychotherapy like PSST in handling problem behaviours such as aggression.
2. Secondary school students in the state should be exposed to PSST training manuals to enable them to acquire the right skills to handle challenges of life instead of using aggression.
3. Teachers, counsellors, and parents should be encouraged to use psychological intervention like PSST instead of punishment to control aggressive behaviours of students/wards.
4. PSST as a single therapy is not effective in handling all the different dimensions of aggression, its use should target the dimensions of aggression it can handle.
5. PSST along with other psychotherapy techniques would be most effective in handling all the different dimensions of aggression.
6. PSST should be used to control students' aggressive behaviours irrespective of gender.

Abdulmalik, J., Ani, C., Ademola, A.J. & Omigbodun, O. (2016). Effects of problem-solving interventions on aggressive behaviours among primary school pupils in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Child and Adolescents Psychiatry and Mental Health* <http://dio.org/10.1186/513034-016-0116-5>. R

The American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry (2022) *Physical Punishment*. www.aacap.org.

Ajah, M. O. (2019). Effect of behavioural therapies on aggressive behaviours of secondary school students in Calabar, Nigeria. An unpublished Ph.D thesis in Faculty of Education University of Calabar, Nigeria.

Ang, R. (2010). Social problem-solving skill-training: Does it really work. *Journal of Child Care in Practice*, 9(1): 5-13.

Anliaks, S. & Sahium, D. (2010). An observational study for evaluating the effect of interpersonal PSST on behavioural dimensions. *Journal of Early Child Development and Care*, 180(8): 995-1003.

Brown, S., Fite, J.P. & Poquiz, J. (2016). Moderating effects of gender on outcomes associated with stressful life: Events among elementary school-age Youth Child *Psychiatry & Human Development*, 47(4): 593-602.

Bushman, B.B. & Peacock, G.G. (2010). Does teaching problem-solving skill matter? An evaluation of problem-solving skill training for the treatment of social and behavioural problem in children? *Journal of Child and Family Behaviour Therapy*, 3(2): 103-124

Cuijpers, P., Weisz, E., Twisk, J. & Hollon, S.D. (2014). Gender as predictor and moderator outcomes in cognitive behaviour therapy and pharmacotherapy for adult depression; An individual patient data meta-analysis. *Depression and Anxiety*, 31(11): 941-957.

Daryoush, G., D'Souza, L. & Ebrahim, S. (2012). Effectiveness of rational emotive therapy on shyness: of gender. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 38(1): 169-173.

De Frutos, T.H. (2013). Five independents' variables affecting bullying: Neighbourhood, family, school, gender-age and mass media. *Sociology Mind* 3(4):304-313

Ikwuba, A. (2011). Review of causes and effects of bullying and way forward in its management in Nigeria. *The Nigeria Educational Psychologist*, 9: 9-15.

Johnston, J. (2016). Can you unlearn a behaviour? www.talkingaboutbehaviour.com.

Knopp, J. & Bower, P. (2013). A systematic review of predictors and moderators of response to psychological therapies in OCD: Do we have enough empirical evidence to target treatment. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 33(8): 1067-1081.

Landenberger, N. A. & Lipsey, M.W. (2005). The positive effects of cognitive-behavioural programs for offenders: a meta-analysis of factors associated with effective treatment. *Journal of Experimental Criminology*, 1: 451-476.

Obikeze, N.I. & Obi, I.F. (2015). Prevalence and incidence of aggressive behaviour among adolescents of senior secondary schools in Anambara State. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 6(2): 139-145.

- Ojewola, F-O (2014). The influence of family condition, gender, and age on the aggressive behaviour of adolescents proves to violent media in Ogbomosho, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(32): 144-155.
- Okon, M.O. (2010). *Psychosocial instigators of aggressive tendencies among university students in the South- south geo-political zone of Nigeria*. Ph.D Thesis, University of Calabar.
- Smeets, K.C., (2017). *Subtyping aggression and predicting cognitive behavioural treatment response in adolescents: What works for whom?* Colofon Publisher.
- Smeets, K.C., Leeijen, A.A., van der Molen, M.J., Scheepers, F.E., Buitelaar, J.k. & Rommelse, N.N. (2014). Treatment moderators of cognitive therapy to reduce aggressive behaviour: a meta-analysis. *European Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 24(3): 255-264.
- Smeets, K.C., Leeijen, A.A., van der Molen, M.J., Scheepers, F.E., Buitelaar, J.k. & Rommelse, N.N. (2015). Treatment moderators of cognitive behaviour therapy to reduce aggressive behaviour: a meta-analysis. *European Child and Adolescent Psychology*, 24(3), 255-264.
- Shreem, F. & Safiana, K.M. (2015). Causes of students' aggressive behaviour at secondary school level. *Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics*, 11: 49-65.
- Spiegler, M. D. & Guevremont, D.K. (2003). *Contemporary behaviour therapy*. (4th ed.) Wadsworth Thomson Learning, Belmont, CA.
- Farrier, N., Kinney, C. McCarthy, E., Humphreys, L. Wittrowski, A, & Morris, J. (2000). Two-year follow-up on cognitive behavioural therapy and supportive counseling in the treatment of persistent symptoms in chronic schizophrenia. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 68: 917-922.
- Tutor2u, (2021). Aggression: Social Learning Theory www.tutor2u.net Retrieve 09/08/2022
- Weisz, J.R., Weiss, B., Han, S.S., Granger, D.A. & Morton, T. (1995). Effects of psychotherapy with children and adolescents revisited. A meta-analysis of treatment outcome studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 117(3): 450-4

Okon, M.O. (2010). The influence of family condition, gender, and age on the aggressive behaviour of adolescents proves to violent media in Ogbomosho, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(32): 144-155.

Smeets, K.C., (2017). *Psychosocial instigators of aggressive tendencies among university students in the South-south geo-political zone of Nigeria*. Ph.D Thesis, University of Calabar.

Smeets, K.C., Leeijen, A.A., van der Molen, M.J., Scheepers, F.E., Buitelaar, J.k. & Rommelse, N.N. (2014). Treatment moderators of cognitive therapy to reduce aggressive behaviour: a meta-analysis. *European Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 24(3): 255-264.

Smeets, K.C., Leeijen, A.A., van der Molen, M.J., Scheepers, F.E., Buitelaar, J.k. & Rommelse, N.N. (2015). Treatment moderators of cognitive behaviour therapy to reduce aggressive behaviour: a meta-analysis. *European Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 24(3), 255-264.

Shireem, F. & Safiana, K.M. (2015). Causes of students' aggressive behaviour at secondary school level. *Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics*, 11: 49-65.

Spiegler, M. D. & Guevremont, D.K. (2003). *Contemporary behaviour therapy*. (4th ed.) Wadsworth Thomson Learning, Belmont, CA.

Umer, N., Kinney, C. McCarthy, E., Humphreys, L. Wittrowski, A, & Morris, J. (2000). Two-year follow-up on cognitive behavioural therapy and supportive counseling in the treatment of persistent symptoms in chronic schizophrenia. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 68: 917-922.

Wadsworth, (2021). Aggression: Social Learning Theory www.tutor2u.net Retrieve